

Electrical Conductance in Molten Salts. Part VII† Sodium nitrate-Strontium nitrate Mixtures

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Electrical conductance of molten mixtures of sodium nitrate with strontium nitrate has been measured. The relative decrease in equivalent conductance ($\Delta \Lambda / \Lambda$), caused by the addition of divalent ions e.g. Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Ca^{2+} to molten sodium nitrate and observed to be inversely proportional to the radius of the divalent ion. Partial equivalent conductivities of the constituents were computed. The enthalpy of activation for equivalent conductance ($\Delta H^\ddagger$) varied slightly with temperature.

TOWARDS an attempt to establish quantitative relation between the observed changes in the equivalent conductance with divalent ion content in molten binary nitrate mixtures¹⁻⁵, the results for sodium nitrate-strontium nitrate mixtures are reported in this communication.

Experimental :

Details regarding the pretreatment of salts, sample preparation, and mode of measurements were essentially similar to those reported earlier¹⁻⁶.

Results and Discussion :

The observed solution resistances (R_p) were corrected for capacitative reactance (C_p) to yield solution resistance (R_s), through the use of expression¹

$$R_s = \frac{R_p}{1 + (R_p C_p 2\pi f)^2}$$

in which f , frequency of ac signal was 1000 Hz.

Specific conductance (k) data for molten mixtures containing sodium and strontium nitrates are presented in Table 1. Equivalent conductances (Λ) were computed using the equivalent volume data of McAuley *et al.*⁷. Plots of Λ versus equivalent fraction (x') of strontium nitrate in the mixtures showed concavity relative to x' -axis; which indicated the presence of weak ordering tendencies in the melt. Λ - x' data could be expressed by equation of the type

$$\Lambda = A + Bx' + Cx'^2$$

Typical values of the coefficients A , B and C , at 450° were 74.52, -103.1 and 50.4 respectively. The partial equivalent conductivities of the two constituents were evaluated by using eqs :

$$\bar{\Lambda} \text{NaNO}_3 = A - Cx'^2$$

$$\bar{\Lambda} \text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2 = A + B + 2Cx' - Cx'^2$$

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE DATA FOR SODIUM NITRATE-STRONTIUM NITRATE MIXTURES.

t°C	k _m	x' = 0.120			t°C	x' = 0.333			x' = 0.462			k _c	V	Λ		
		k _c	V	Λ		k _m	k _c	V	Λ	k _c	V				Λ	
292.5	0.7545				341.8	0.6315										
296.0	0.7832				350.0	—			0.6680	43.39	28.99	443.5	0.8206			
300.0	—	0.7952	43.62	34.69	375.0	—			0.7714	43.77	33.76	450.0	—	0.8511	44.17	37.59
325.0	—	0.9069	44.04	39.94	400.0	—			0.8649	44.15	38.19	468.8	0.9392			
331.8	0.9391				402.0	0.8735						475.0	—	0.9682	44.53	43.11
340.5	0.9783				425.0	—			0.9486	44.53	42.24					
350.0	—	1.0116	44.46	44.98	438.0	0.9857										
363.5	1.0689				450.0	—			1.0224	44.91	45.91					
367.5	1.0730				451.0	1.0265										
375.0	—	1.1093	44.88	49.78												
380.5	1.1354															
391.8	1.1653															
400.0	—	1.200	45.29	54.35												
425.0	—	1.2836	45.71	58.67												
428.2	1.2996															
435.5	1.3143															
443.0	1.3365															
450.0	—	1.3601	46.13	62.74												
475.0	—	1.4297	46.55	66.55												
479.5	1.4360															
482.5	1.4526															

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and are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PARTIAL EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE FOR NaNO_3 & $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ at 450° .

x'	$\bar{\Lambda}_{\text{NaNO}_3}$	$\bar{\Lambda}_{\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2}$
0.0	74.52	-28.53
0.1	74.016	-19.00
0.2	72.50	-9.44
0.3	69.98	-2.88
0.5	61.92	+ 9.22
1.0	24.12	+21.82
(extrapolated)		

TABLE 3— $\Delta H^\ddagger$ VALUES FOR NaNO_3 - $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ MIXTURES.

Eq. Fraction ($\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$)	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kcal/g. eq) 623 K	723 K
0.0	3.19	2.80
0.120	3.65 (3.69 ^a , 3.41 ^b)	3.38
0.333	4.60 (4.74 ^a , 4.19 ^b)	4.40
0.462	—	5.74

The variation of Λ and $\bar{\Lambda}$'s with x' are shown in Fig. 1.

a ; NaNO_3 - $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ system, ref. 1
b ; NaNO_3 - $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ system, ref. 3

Fig. 1. Variation of equivalent (Λ), partial equivalent ($\bar{\Lambda}$), excess ($\Delta\Lambda$) conductance with x' , for NaNO_3 - $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ mixtures.

A direct calculation of excess conductivity was not possible for want of equivalent conductance of $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, but, when the Λ - x' and $\bar{\Lambda}_{\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2}$ - x' plots are extrapolated to $x'=1$ [pure $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ state], two curves meet at the same point yielding a value of $21.8 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ for equivalent conductance of $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. Excess equivalent conductances at various x' are also plotted in Fig. 1. A comparison of Λ values for NaNO_3 melts to which Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and

Ca^{2+} ions in the form of nitrate were added (Fig. 2) clearly shows that the fall in conductance (at any composition) is in the order $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Sr}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+}$. The relative decrease in equivalent conductance ($\Delta\Lambda/\Lambda$) is found to vary with r_4^{-1} of the divalent ion. (Fig. 3).

Log Λ vs $1/T$ plots were slightly curved indica-

*Strontium nitrate decomposes before it melts.

Fig. 2. Equivalent conductance vs equivalent fraction of divalent ion, for (1) $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$; (2) $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (3) $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ systems.

Fig. 3. Relative decrease in equivalent conductance ($\Delta\Lambda/\Lambda$) as a function of x_2^{-1}

ting the temperature dependence of $\Delta H^\ddagger$. Values for $\overline{\Delta H^\ddagger}$ at two typical temperatures are shown in Table 3. At a given temperature, increase in $\Delta H^\ddagger$ values with strontium nitrate content could be considered as a reflection of increased electrostriction of the medium. $\Delta H^\ddagger$ values for $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-(Ba, Ca)}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ system at some common temperatures and divalent ion content are also included for comparison. Although these values reflect the order $\text{NaNO}_3\text{-Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{NaNO}_3\text{-Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2 > \text{NaNO}_3\text{-Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, but the variation is so small that no quantitative relation could be established.

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